

CONSTITUTIONAL-LEGAL BASIS OF THE RESPONSIBILITY OF STATE BODIES AND OFFICIALS TO SOCIETY AND CITIZENS IN THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN

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Annotation: the article examines such issues as universal concepts regarding the responsibility of state bodies and their officials in the provision of human rights and freedoms in the Republic of Uzbekistan, legal, including certain constitutional and legal aspects of the responsibility of state bodies to increase the responsibility of society to society, the effective application of constitutional and legal responsibility to society and citizens in

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In the process of democratic reforms in Uzbekistan, the issue of achieving the responsibility of state bodies and officials to society and citizens occupies one of the central places. The priority tasks in this regard are the ideas of the head of our state that "the people should serve the people of the state bodies, and not the government agencies," the strategy of action for the further development of the Republic of Uzbekistan¹, then the idea of "State-for man" was embodied in the development strategy of the new Uzbekistan, and then in the constitutional reforms implemented on the principle of "Man-society-state"².

For this reason, the priority of values was redistributed. If earlier it was first declared as the interests of the state, then society, and only then the interests of the individual, and now a system of values was established, which was first the interests of the individual, then society, and only then the interests of the state. These principles formed the basis of the development strategy of the new Uzbekistan.

This new paradigm led to the establishment of the status of society and the state, relying on it, while advancing priority ideas, revising the constitutive principles and directing more towards the interests of the individual. The expansion of the constitutional guarantees of the participation of citizens in the management of the affairs of the state and society makes the issue of the formation of their socio-cultural competencies relevant. This issue sets the task of developing the culture of behavior of the individual in a society that creates the motivation of the main value between the subjects of the constitutive-legal relations, that is, the individual, society and the state.

¹ Ўзбекистон Республикаси Президентининг 2017 йил 7 февралдаги ПФ-4947-сон "Ўзбекистон Республикасини янада ривожлантириш бўйича Ҳаракатлар стратегияси тўғрисида"ги фармони // <https://lex.uz/acts/3107036>.

² Ўзбекистон Республикаси Президентининг 2022 йил 28 январдаги ПФ-60-сон «2022 — 2026 йилларга мўлжалланган Янги Ўзбекистоннинг тараққиёт стратегияси тўғрисида» ги Фармони. // Қонунчилик маълумотлари миллий базаси, 29.01.2022 й., 06/22/60/0082-сон

It should be noted that the criteria for values underlying socio-cultural behavior, determined by state norms that take into account social norms, regulate all relations developing in society in a general state. In this case, A.Yu.As Klimanova noted, legal norms prevent violation along with the regulation of social relations³. Each function of the legal norm, which is indicated, has an independent character, but they complement each other, if not one of them, their socially useful significance disappears.

In addition, given that the most important social relations are regulated through the legal norms of the state, it is natural that the subjects of legal relations have a constant desire to violate them. Therefore, it is necessary for the state to take the necessary measures to prevent, identify and eliminate possible violations. To this end, the state also supports sanctions measures against offenders. Thus, it can be concluded that the interstitial-legal responsibility is bi-biased, that is, bulib with a positive and negative view, they are manifested in a separate state, and also together Ham.

In turn, constitutional-legal liability is recognized as one of the independent types of legal liability.

General signs of legal liability are characteristic of criminal, civil, administrative and cross-legal liability. The following types of legal liability, i.e. constitutional - legal liability, have the same structure at their base, which theoretically allows us to define their existence as types of legal liability.

In this case, the following general signs of constitutional - legal liability can be distinguished: firstly, liability occurs only in cases provided for by the norms of the law; secondly, it is possible to apply liability measures for violation of legal norms, including constitutional ones; thirdly, constitutional-legal liability is established in acts of state bodies; fourth, liability is associated with coercive measures of the state; ; sixth, constitutionality is a state of legality in the application of legal liability measures. At the same time, it should be noted that constitutional-legal liability, unlike other types of legal liability, has a more political aspect. Subjects and measures of political and constitutional-legal responsibility can be combined. However, this does not mean replacing or matching political and cross-legal responsibility, but rather that cross-legal responsibility is exercised in the field of political relations.

The Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan manifests itself as the foundation of all types of legal liability, including the type of liability expressed in the sectoral norms of one of its types, constitutional law, which is also part of its order. The sectoral nature of constitutional-legal liability is manifested in the clarification of the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan by legislative acts and acts of the Constitutional Court of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

The foundations of civil and legal responsibility of state bodies and officials to society and citizens occupy a central place in the theory of responsibility. On this issue P.I.As Kuchura correctly noted: "it is the basis of the occurrence of liability that is one of the signs that

³ Климанова А.Ю. Конституционно-правовое регулирование формирования экономической основы местного самоуправления: автореферат дис. ... кандидата юридических наук. - Москва, 2013. – Б.53.

distinguish one type of legal liability from another, as well as the most important element of a particular type of liability"⁴.

This means that it is the aspect of legal liability that distinguishes one type of legal liability from another, and as a result, an important element of one or another type of liability can be the basis for its occurrence. In turn, the basis for the occurrence of any liability is a violation of the rules of mandatory behavior-an offense, which has always been expressed in the norm of the law.

Only the basic principles and rules of all types of legal liability are enshrined in the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan. The Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan cannot be the only source of criminal, civil-legal, administrative, disciplinary and constitutional-legal liability. The Constitution, however, places more emphasis on the regulation of constitutional - legal liability in relation to criminal liability . The norms of constitutional law provide a meaningful basis for the norms of other branches of law, regulating the most basic, fundamental social relations.

Based on the constitutional-legal status of state authorities and officials, priority is given to their final results, and achievement of results can be the basis for applying legal liability measures to them. The constitutional-legal obligation of state authorities and their officials is a legal notice to the subject in order to achieve (obtain) a certain positive result within his competence.

In general, it can be said that interstitial-legal responsibility is not limited to the interstitial-legal framework itself, it arises, develops and is achieved through its introduction in interstitial-legal, i.e., sectoral legal relations. Also, a large number of sanctions (positive or negative) are gaining the most accurate and developed system of higher, local, citizens ' self-government bodies and cross-legal sanctions, and it can be taken as the basis for the development of a theory of positive legal responsibility.aimed at changing the powers of their officials.

⁴ Кучура П.И. К вопросу об основаниях конституционно-правовой ответственности / Государство и право: теория и практика: материалы Междунар. науч. конф. (г. Чита, март 2013 г.). - Чита: Издательство Молодой ученый, 2013. — С. 20-23.

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